

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

DISSEMINATION AND TRAINING RESULTS

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVEAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

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WHAT IS PIMIC-ITN

PIMIC is a cooperative effort led by a team that consists of medievalists specialising in Western, Byzantine and Islamic history tackling a vital historical question as a starting point and questioning it throughout the project: Why did the Christendom government and society develop certain processes of institutionalisation that did not characterise the Islamic world, considering that the early medieval situation might have suggested otherwise?

The main challenge of the team consisted in providing possible answers to this problematic question, avoiding conceptual bypasses, evolutionary or teleological models, simplistic oppositions and dyadic narratives (East/West, Christendom/Islam, etc.) biases which often underlie traditional historiographies and socio-institutional approaches. This project conceived of institutions as structures or processes performed by social regularities, which do not simply flow from an aggregation of individual behaviours, but rather as the outcome of power struggles among multiple actors who shape institutions as arenas of social conflict and dispute. The members of the project drew at least four clear areas of research: a) methodological one, (de)constructing the concept of institution itself; b) legal institutions and the codification of law; c) economic institutions and state funding strategies; d) self-representation of power institutions and their physical embodiments

Through such formulation, PIMIC has attempted to create a social awareness of the need to understand institutional diversity as a means to promote a deeper appreciation of the different political cultures prevailing in a global world.

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In addition to academic activities, the PIMIC ITN's interests have been oriented towards the dissemination of its scientific results.

Experienced Researchers, working in common with their employers, the PIMIC audiovisual and publishing private partners, have designed and implemented ambitious schemes for the diffusion and transfer of the PIMIC ITN's results. For this purpose, Early Stage Researchers and Experienced Researchers not only have been inside an intense formative activity in the most demanding requirements of their own disciplines but also they have been the first participants in two innovative and comprehensive training programmes: the Media School for Historians and the Publishing School for Historians.

In addition to this, it is important to emphasise that PIMIC outreach activities focus on the transfer of knowledge, communication as well as project cooperation. Thus, all members of the project have contributed to the design, development and implementation of both the travelling exhibition *The Way We Are Ruled* and the PIMIC courseware *Why Institutions Matter*. Therefore, alongside new books and articles, PIMIC offers to lecturers and teachers anywhere in the world practical tool for teaching and learning.

Having all this in mind, PIMIC Project aimed to create a new generation of PhD fellows, qualified to develop their scholarly work from groundbreaking perspectives and by means of a comparative approach, but also equipped to respond to new social, political and cultural challenges. PIMIC young researchers have been trained to communicate their results to a wide array of audiences.

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**PHD DISSERTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, CONFERENCES AND
SEMINAR TALKS**

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1. PIMIC FELLOWS

1.1 EXPERIENCED RESEARCHERS

KATE HAMMOND

ER BRILL PUBLISHERS

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/kate-hammond>

Dr. Kate Hammond held a two-year fellowship under the Marie Curie EU-funded Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom Initial Training Network (PIMIC-ITN), hosted by Brill Academic Publishers (based in Leiden, the Netherlands). She had been working at Brill full-time under the remit of PIMIC since 1 September 2013, as a member of the History Publishing Unit, supervised by Julian Deahl, Senior Acquisitions Editor for Medieval Studies and Military History.

The first year of her fellowship had been focused on editorial training. For most of this time, she had been based in the Brill office, but she had also attended academic conferences in Washington DC, Kalamazoo (both USA), and Leeds (UK) as a Brill trainee editor, and participated fully in PIMIC programme.

Her work focused on the four major areas of academic publishing at Brill, to a greater or lesser extent: books, major reference works, journals, and online.

The major focus of her work for PIMIC was the two Publishing Schools for Historians that Brill run as part of the project (Leiden, October 2014 and Leeds, July 2015), which she co-organised. These took the form of lectures and a series of mock editorial board meetings, which aimed to explain to PIMIC fellows the processes and pitfalls of publishing book manuscripts, journal articles, and chapters in essay volumes.

It was announced in March 2015 that Kate Hammond would succeed Julian Deahl in permanent full-time employment as medieval studies

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editor at Brill at the end of her PIMIC fellowship, role that she continues up to now.

The recruitment of Dr. Kate Hammond by the company Brill Publishers (full member of the project), is considered a success in the employability of the recruited researchers of the PIMIC training program. Dr Kate Hammond obtained a position as a Medieval Studies editor at Brill thanks to her own capabilities as well as her skills result of the formative actions of the project. PIMIC training included a comprehensive set of complementary skills apart from those characteristic of the academic world and also exposed researcher to the private sector, widening in this way the business horizon of the academic sector.

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MARÍA LÓPEZ VILLARQUIDE

ER LÓPEZ LI FILMS

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/maria-lopez-villarquide>

López-Li Films Documentary Film Company collaborated with the PIMIC Project by designing the content of two courses for the ITN fellows, the so called “Media School for Historians”, as well as in its dissemination through media formats.

Dr. María López’s position as Experienced Researcher hired by López-Li, consisted of being a sort of communicative bridge between the people at PIMIC (students, teachers, academic people) and the private sector. She was also being trained in the field of movie making, particularly at the production department.

Committed with the general idea of delivering a short piece of documentary and understanding the “life of a movie” once released, the ITN fellows worked hard on their subjects and on how to translate them to the screen.

The “Media School for Historians 1” had proposed an introduction to the audiovisual material, script writing, recording, editing and pitching a video creation. The twelve ITN fellows had all developed an interesting product from scratch until it became a trailer of what it was going to be their future documentary but now, four months later, they confronted a new challenge: To work on their footage and manage to “sell” a definitive 10 minute documentary to an ideal prospective buyer, which was the aim of the “Media School for Historians 2”. In just two weeks, the ITN fellows focused on their editing stuff while attending to new paths in their academic lives, the “Oral communication strategy” on the one hand and the “Website positioning workshop” on the other.

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1.2 EARLY STAGE RESEARCHERS

EVGENIYA SHELINA

ESR CCHS-CSIC

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/evgeniya-shelina>

PhD : The Lexical Field of Power in the 13th-Century Latin and the Vernaculars (Old French, Old Castilian, and Old Norse)

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- Workshop *Textometry of medieval sources*, Rome, June 2014, Italy. Paper: «Les vocabulaires du pouvoir en Norvège médiévale ».
- *Lleida international medieval meeting*, June 2014, Spain. Paper: “Potestas and Auctoritas in the vernacular: vald in Old Norse”.
- *Leeds International medieval Congress*, July 2014, UK. Paper: “The Vocabularies of Power in the 13th century Norway”
- *Salzburg Religions Triennale on Politics and Religion*, July-August 2014 Austria. Paper: “Medieval Political Thought ».
- *Colloque international Peuple(s) et Pouvoir(s) en représentation dans les espaces germanique et nordique*, Paris, November 2014, France. Paper : « Les vocabulaires du pouvoir en Norvège et en Islande médiévales : une comparaison»
- *Conference Worte - Konzepte - Bedeutungen. Welche Historische Semantik für das Mittelalter?* Frankfurt am Main, February 2015, Germany.

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- *Leeds International medieval Congress*, July 2015, UK. Paper: "Hierarchies among the equals in 13th -century Christendom".
- *Lincoln conference "Law, Custom and Ritual in the Medieval Mediterranean"*, July 2015, UK. Paper: "The Power of Language and the Language of Power in the 13th-Century Castilian Law"
- *Concilium Lateranense*, November 2015, Rome, Italy. Paper: "Hierarchies among Equals in Late Medieval Christendom".
- *Journée Serge Lusignan*, Paris 1, May 2016, France. Paper : « Comparer le comparable et l'incomparable. Les champs sémantiques du pouvoir dans le latin et les langues vernaculaires du XIIIe siècle »
- *Lleida international medieval meeting*, June 2016, Spain. Paper: 'The question is whether you can make words mean so many different things'. The Semantics of Power in the 13th-Century Castile'.
- *Conference Words Don't come easy*, September 2016, Sweden. Paper: "What are the words that serve as pegs to hang ideas about domination on? The Conceptual field(s) of Power in Latin and in Vernaculars in the 13th Century"
- *School for doctoral students on Lexicometry*, Paris 1, June 2015, France

PUBLICATIONS

'The Specificity of the Development of the Church Organisation in Norway' in *Sovremennye problemi izycheniya istorii cerkvi*, Moscow, 2014, pp. 400-411

Accepted:

(2017) The Semantics of Power in Old Norse. The Concept of *Vald*. 1 La sémantique du pouvoir en vieux norrois. Le concept de *vald*. *Revue d'histoire nordique*, "FRAMESPA-CNRS-Université de Toulouse".

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IAN D. MORRIS

ESR CCHS-CSIC

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/ian-david-morris>

PhD : ‘Royal Courts from Late Antiquity to Early Islam’

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- “Courtly Ceremonial and the Crisis of Early Islamic Kingship”, presented at the workshop ‘Caliphs, Sultans, Presidents: Rulers between Religion and Realpolitik throughout Islamic History’, Westfälische Wilhelms-University Muenster. 21 July 2016
- “From *Hājib* to *Cubicularius*: Translating ‘Chamberlains’ in Late Antiquity”, presented at the Mediaeval History Postgraduate Seminar Series, St Andrews. 11 May 2016
- “The Caliphate: Once and Future Empire?”, public lecture and panel at the Chalke Valley History Festival, Salisbury. 25 July 2015
- “Ardashir Doesn’t Live Here Any More: Persian Theory and Arabian Practice at the Early Islamic Court”, presented at the Leeds International Medieval Congress. 7 July 2015
- “The Arabian Origins of the *Hāğib*: From Household Servant to Courtly Officer”, presented at the 4th Nangeroni Meeting, ‘Early Islam: The Sectarian Milieu of Late Antiquity?’, Milan. 16 June 2015
- “Muhammad and the Mythmakers: Critical Approaches to Early Islamic History”, public lecture, University College London. 12 May 2015.
- “The Word of Abraham: Righteous Gentiles and Sectarian Boundaries in the Qur’ān”, guest lecture at Saint Louis University, Madrid campus. 26 March 2015

PUBLICATIONS

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Forthcoming: “Ḥājib”, entry in *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, *THREE*.

In preparation: Journal articles: “The Arabian Origins of the Ḥājib” and “Did the Umayyads have Game Reserves?”; planning to submit summer 2017.

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SARA GREER

ESR UNIVERSITY OF ST. ANDREWS

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/sarah-greer>

PhD: Gandersheim and Quedlinburg: memory and identity in Ottonian Saxony

(Submitted & discussed September 2016)

Postdoctoral Research Fellow, St. Andrews University: Having submitted her doctoral thesis in September 2016, Sarah Greer will continue her connection with both the School of History at St Andrews and the EU. She has been selected as the postdoctoral research fellow under the supervision of Professor MacLean as part of the new HERA-funded research network: '[After Empire: Using and Not Using the Past in the Tenth Century](#)'

<https://standrewsschoolofhistory.wordpress.com/2016/11/23/postdoc-spotlight-sarah-greer/>

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- 23rd International Medieval Congress, University of Leeds, 'Guess who's coming to dinner: the stolen feast at Werla and the succession dispute of 1002'; July 2016
- Borderlines XX Postgraduate Medieval Conference Dublin, 'Reassessing the past in the *Primordia* of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim', April 2016
- Mediaeval History Postgraduate Seminar Series, St. Andrews, 'Reassessing the past in the *Primordia* of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim', March 2016
- Mediaeval History Postgraduate Seminar Series, , St. Andrews, 'Bride-taking and law-breaking: justice and gender in the regency of Mathilda of Quedlinburg', September 2015

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- 22nd International Medieval Congress, University of Leeds, 'Reassessing the past in the *Primordia* of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim' July 2015
- *Gender and Transgression in the Middle Ages* Postgraduate Conference, University of St Andrews, 'Bride-taking and law-breaking: justice and gender in the regency of Mathilda of Quedlinburg', May 2015
- *Adel und Herrschaft im 10. Jahrhundert westlich und östlich des Rheims*, Deutsches Historisches Institut Paris 'Ottonian female rulership and the regency of Mathilda of Quedlinburg', April 2015
- Mediaeval Postgraduate Seminar Series, St. Andrews 'Guess Who's Coming to Dinner: Stolen Feasts and Succession Politics in Ottonian Germany' March 2015
- University of Auckland Department of Classics and Ancient History Seminar Series 'A Cloister for Holy Maidens and a Triumphant Peace for the Realm: representations of the past in the *Primordia* of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim', July 2014
- *Revealing Records VI*, King's College London 'Nostris spes et dominatrix: representations of female monastic patronage in the historical works of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim', May 2014
- Medieval Postgraduate Seminar Series St. Andrews, 'A Foreign Exchange: The role of Irish pilgrim monks in Frankish female monasteries', February 2014
- Mediaeval Postgraduate Seminar Series, St. Andrews, 'Lost in Translation: The use of Benedict, Columbanus and Caesarius in rules for early medieval female monasteries', October 2013.

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CORY HITT

ESR UNIVERSITY OF ST. ANDREWS

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/cory-hitt>

PhD: Models of Norm Transmission in 12th- and 13th- Century Old French and Anglo-Norman Literature and Law

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- “*On seignier/ Enseignier: Wordplay in Chrétien de Troyes’ Le Roman de Perceval*”, given at the International Medieval Symposium-Paris, June 2016
- “Common Blood and Knightly Bloodlines: Institutionalized Norms and Status Law in Anglo-Norman and Old French Legal Codes”, given at the Institute of Legal and Constitutional Research “Law & Society Colloquium”, June 2016.
- “Burning Breasts: Mothers as Counsel-Givers in Old French and Anglo-Norman Literature”, given at the Gender & Medieval Studies Conference, University of Hull, January 2016.
- “Transmission of Norms in *L’Histoire de Guillaume le Maréchal*”, given at Leeds International Medieval Congress, University of Leeds, July 2015.

PUBLICATIONS

“Burning Breasts: Grieving Mothers as Counsel-Givers in Old French and Anglo-Norman Literature”, to be published in a forthcoming edited volume on Gender & Emotion, 2017-2018

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JASMIN HAUCK

ESR UNIVERSITY OF ROMA TRE

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/jasmin-hauck>

PhD: "Florentine Marriage Dispensations (1460-1540). A socio-legal history"

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- *The social representation of legal knowledge. Scientia and ignorantia in the registers of the papal penitentiary* (Legal and social issues in context. PIMIC-workshop in Rom, May 2014).
- *Le dispense matrimoniali di Firenze, 1460-1530. Una storia giuridica e sociale* (WinterSchool: Studi mediterranei fra teoria e prassi, Workshop DHI Rome, 23-27 February 2015).
- *Yan Thomas, Les opérations du droit: The paradigm of legal fictionality* (Seminar PIMIC: A reading that shaped my research, Roma Tre, 21 May 2015).
- *Marriage Dispensations and Marriage Customs in the late medieval Diocese of Florence* (Session "Power & Institutions in Medieval Islam & Christendom (PIMIC), IV: Power, Institutions, and Canon Law in Byzantine and Medieval Contexts", International Medieval Congress, Leeds 6-9 July 2015).
- *Anticipated retroactivity: Marital identity and the disponability of time. Some observations on late medieval Florentine marriage dispensations* (Session 7.1: Comparative aspects on the institutionalisation of law - the Mediterranean in the middle ages 3: Law in Social Contexts, at the Society for the Medieval Mediterranean Conference, Lincoln 13-15 July 2015).
- *Les délégués du concile. Une biographie collective* (Perpignan 1415 : un sommet européen à l'époque des conciles, Colloque international organisé par Aymat Catafau - Nikolas Jaspert - Thomas Wetzstein, Perpignan 23-25 September 2015).

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- *Buchpräsentation (with Emanuele Conte, Giuliano Milani, Arnaud Fossier) zu Marta Madero, La loi de la chair. Le droit au corps du conjoint dans l'œuvre des canonistes (XII^e-XV^e siècle), Paris 2015 (Seminaire "Casuistique", organized by Paolo Napoli, Emanuele Conte, EHESS, 11 February 2016).*
- *Gnade nach Aktenlage. Ehedispense im spätmittelalterlichen Florenz zwischen Norm und Praxis (Forschungskolloquium Historisches Seminar der KU Eichstätt-Ingolstadt, April 2016)*
- *Le choix du procureur et l'exécution des dispenses matrimoniales. Statut matrimonial et manipulation du temps (International Congress of Medieval Canon Law, Paris Junie2016).*

PUBLICATIONS

Review "Fernanda Alfieri, Nella camera degli sposi. Tomás Sánchez, il matrimonio, la sessualità (secoli XVI-XVII), Bologna 2010", in: Annales de démographie historique 128 (2014), p. 221-223.

Review "Marta Madero, La loi de la chair. Le droit au corps du conjoint dans l'œuvre des canonistes (XII^e - XV^e siècle) Paris, Publications de la Sorbonne 2015", in : Annales de démographie historique [accepted for publication].

La nomination des délégués conciliaires auprès du pape Benoît XIII (1415). Appartenances multiples et jeux de pouvoir au Concile de Constance, in: Perpignan 1415. Un sommet européen à l'époque des conciles, ed. Aymat Catafau - Nikolas Jaspert - Thomas Wetzstein, 2017 [accepted for publication].

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RASMUS BECH OLSEN

ESR BIRKBECK COLLEGE

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/rasmus-bech-olsen>

PhD: Sultanic Rule as Symbolic Practice - Imposing, Opposing and Negotiating Rulership in 13th-14th Century Damascus.

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- Reading a Mamluk Protest - Paper at Birkbeck HCA Graduate Research Day , Birkbeck HCA Graduate Research Day 2014, Department of History Classics and Archeology, Birkbeck College, University of London 01/12 2014
- The Friday preacher as socio-political actor: A case from 14th century Damascus, Annual conference of British Association for Islamic Studies (BRAIS), Senate House Bloomsbury, London 14th of April 2015
- Of Just Kings and Pious Commoners - The construction of a conservative urban utopia in *Sīrat al-Malik al-Zāhir Baybars*, Heroic Narratives Conference , University of Copenhagen, 12th of June 2015
- Power and Protest in Mamluk Syria, International Medieval Conference, University of Leeds, 8th of July 2015, Chronicles as sources for rituals in the early Mamluk period, Biennial conference of the Society for the Medieval Mediterranean, University of Lincoln, UK, 14th of July 2015
- “Mamluk Politics as Spatial Practice: Creating a Ceremonial Topography in 14th century Damascus”, Annual conference of British Association for Islamic Studies (BRAIS), Senate House Bloomsbury, London 11th of April 2016

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- The Sultan and the City: The Topography of Power in Mamluk Damascus 1250 - 1400, Annual Conference of the American Association of Middle Eastern Studies, Marriot Hotel, Boston MA 17th of November 2016

PUBLICATIONS

“Review of A. Elbendary’s *Crowds and Sultans: Urban Protest in Medieval Egypt and Syria*, Cairo 2016” in *al-Masāq: Journal of the Medieval Mediterranean* (forthcoming).

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TOMMI LANKILA

ESR UNIVERSITY OF ROMA TOR VERGATA

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/tommi-lankila>

PhD: Saracen Maritime Raids (Ghazawat) in the Early Medieval Central Mediterranean

Submitted, to be discussed in May 2017 (University of Princeton)

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- Apr 2016 Deutsches Historisches Institut in Rom, a conference paper on An overview of 'Saracen Raids' in Southern Italy and the Early Medieval Central Mediterranean
- Jul 2015 University of Lincoln, a conference paper on Islamic Law and 'Saracen Raids' in the early medieval Central Mediterranean at conference Society for Medieval Mediterranean 2015
- Jul 2015 University of Leeds, a conference paper on Religion, war, and law - Islamic Raids in the Central Mediterranean at International Medieval Congress of Leeds (IMC)
- Feb 2015 Deutsches Historisches Institut in Rom, a conference paper on Islamic Maritime Raiding in the Mediterranean - Transference from the 'Other Mediterranean' to the 'Classic Mediterranean'
- May 2014 University of Rome Tor Vergata and Roma Tre, a conference paper on Saracen mentions in the chartulae of Cava de' Tirreni at conference Legal and Social Issues in Context (PIMIC Marie Curie conference)
- Apr 2014 Princeton University, a conference paper on Towards the Great Land: Early Medieval Italy and its Visitors from the Saracen World at conference There and Back Again: Travel, Itinerancy, and Adventure in the Middle Ages

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PUBLICATIONS:

Forthcoming translation of the professor dissertation *Carmen Elegiacum Ibnu-L-Faridi cum commentario Abdu-L-Ghanyi* of Professor G. A. Wallin (1850). From Latin to Swedish, together with M. Th. Tom Bergman. Published in *Georg August Wallin Skrifter 7. (G. A. Wallin's Writings 7)*. K. Öhrnberg & P. Berg (eds), in print fall 2016

Submitted article “Saracen Mercenaries - The religious legitimacy of Muslim mercenaries in the South Italian context in the early Middle Ages,” in *Al-Masāq. Journal of the Medieval Mediterranean*

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ATTILIO STELLA

ESR TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/attilio-stella>

PhD : “Signoria ecclesiastica e comunità rurali nel medioevo (sec. XII-XIII). San Giorgio in Braida di Verona e i villaggi del Fiumenovo”.

Submitted and discussed in May 2014, Trento.

Postdoctoral Research Fellow. Dr. Attilio Stella is currently a post doctoral fellow at the University of Verona.

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- “Rethinking ‘The’ Medieval State,” Roundtable at the PIMIC-ITN Final Forum, 24-25 June 2016, London, Mary Ward House.
- “Feudalesimo e *consuetudo* fra scienza legale e scienza sociale,” undergraduate lecture, 31 March 2016, Trento, Università degli Studi.
- “Oralidad y escritura. La costumbre y su normatividad en los juristas feudales de Italia y Francia (siglos XII-XIII),” postgraduate lecture, 16 March 2016, Vitoria-Gasteiz, Universidad del País Vasco.
- “Re-thinking Custom and Law. The *Summa Feudorum* of Iacobus de Ardizone in Local and European Context,” paper, 24 February 2016, International Conference *Medieval Europe in Motion 3. Circulations juridiques et pratiques artistiques, intellectuelles et culturelles dans l’Europe au Moyen Âge (XIIIe - XVe siècles)*, Lisbon, 24-26 February 2016.
- “Orality vs. Literacy? Social Practice, Feudal Lawyers and the Problem of Normativity in 13th-Century Italy and France,” frontal lecture, 28 January 2016, Madrid, CCHS-CSIC.

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- “Is Feudalism Dead? Rituals, Customs and Laws of Fiefs in Medieval Italy,” paper at *Law, Custom, and Ritual in the Medieval Mediterranean*, Session 5.1 of the Conference of the Society for the Medieval Mediterranean, Lincoln, 13-15 July 2015).
- “Vassals, Knights, and Squires. From Local Customs to Law in 13th c. Italy,” paper, 8 July 2015, *PIMIC V. Making Law, Controlling Violence in the Middle Ages*, Session 1025, International Medieval Congress (Leeds, 5-10 July 2015).
- “The Vanishing Wood. Augustinians Canons, Land Exploiters in the Late Medieval and Early Modern Venetian State,” paper, 3 July 2015, *Greening History. Studying the Environment across Disciplines: Past, Present and Future*, Session 9-H. *Monasteries and the Environment I: Exploiting Natural Resources - Shaping Landscapes* (ESEH Conference, Versailles, 30 June - 3 July 2015).
- “Susan Reynolds’ Fiefs and Vassals: Legal fiction or social practices?” paper, 28 May 2015, *A reading that shaped my research: PIMIC seminars in Rome, Roma Tre* (21 and 28 May 2015).
- “Signoria ecclesiastica fra giurisdizione vescovile e comunale. Il confine veronese-vicentino nel XII secolo,” paper at the Conference *Vescovi nell’XI secolo: il caso di Bobbio, le dinamiche del potere, i rapporti con il territorio* (Trento, 16 October 2014).
- “The settlement of disputes and its interpretative outcomes. A case study from northern Italy (12-13th c.),” paper at the Conference *Legal and Social Issues in Context* (École Française de Rome, 30 May 2014).

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ORGANISATION OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE SESSIONS

- Organisation and coordination of a macro-session of three panels - of three talks each - at the Conference of the Society for the Medieval Mediterranean *Law, Custom and Ritual in the Medieval Mediterranean* (Lincoln, 13-15 July 2015).
- Macro-session's title: "Comparative Aspects on the Institutionalisation of Law - the *Mediterraneum* in the Middle Ages". These are the three panels:
 - 1: The Making of Political Discourses. Session 2.1 (13 July)
 - 2: The Production of Legal Knowledge. Session 5.1 (14 July)
 - 3: Law in Social Contexts. Session 7.1 (15 July)
 - 2. Organisation of a session at the International Medieval Congress (Leeds, 5-10 July 2015)
- Power & Institutions in Medieval Islam & Christendom, V: Making Law, Controlling Violence in the Middle Ages, Session 1025 (8 July)

PUBLICATIONS

A. Stella, "The circulation of the *Libri Feudorum* in the thirteenth century," manuscript based on my talk at *Medieval Europe in Motion - 3*, proceedings of the Conference *Circulations juridiques et pratiques artistiques, intellectuelles et culturelles dans l'Europe au Moyen Âge (XIIIe - XVe siècles)*, Lisbon (24-26 February 2016) (in preparation)

A. Stella, "Creating Customs. Social Practice, Oral Norms, and the Codification of Feudal Law (1150-1250)," concluded, to be submitted to a relevant journal.

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A. Stella, “The *Liber Ardizonis*. Reshaping the *Libri Feudorum* in the Early Thirteenth Century,” concluded, to be submitted to the journal *Tijdschrift voor Rechtsgeschiedenis*.

A. Stella, “Nota sugli antichi possessi dell’arcidiacono veronese Adelberto-Aceli a Nomi e Gardumo (1021, 1028),” *Studi Trentini. Storia*, 95:1 (2016)

A. Stella, “Transhumant Sheep Farming and Seigniorial Economy in the Veronese pre-Alps (12-14th c.),” in: *Invisible Cultures: Historical and Archaeological Perspectives*, Cambridge 2015, 150-76.

G.M. Varanini, A. Stella, “Scenari veronesi per la *Summa feudorum* di Iacopo di Ardizzone da Broilo,” in: *Honos alit artes. Studi per il settantesimo compleanno di Mario Ascheri. La formazione del diritto comune*,” Firenze 2014, 255-280.

Review of S. Carocci, *Signorie di Mezzogiorno. Società rurali, poteri aristocratici e monarchia (XII-XIII secolo)*, *Archivio della Società Romana di Storia Patria*, 137: 121-6 (2014)

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ADRIAN VIALE

ESR UNIVERSITÉ PARIS 1 -PANTHÉON- SORBONNE

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/adrian-viale>

PhD: La papauté et les institutions politiques et ecclésiastiques de l'Empire byzantine, VIe-VIIIe siècles.

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- “Considérations sur les *apocrisaires* romains à Constantinople”
23rd International Congress of Byzantine Studies, Belgrade, 22-27/08/2016
- “Women in the Liber Pontificalis” Gender and Transgression in the Middle Ages, University of St. Andrews, 26-28/04/2016
- “La papauté byzantine: éléments pour une analyse institutionnelle”
Ville édition des rencontres internationales des doctorants en études byzantines. Paris, 2-3/10/2015
- “Legal Elements in Papal-Imperial Communication (6th-7th Centuries)”.
Society for Medieval Mediterranean Conference 2015. University of Lincoln 13-15/07/2015
- “The Institutional Identity of the Papacy and the Lateran Council of 649”.
Leeds International Medieval Congress 2015. University of Leeds, 6-9/07/2015
- “Coming Together or Breaking Apart? Papacy and Empire in the Age of Justinian”
Leeds International Medieval Congress 2014. University of Leeds, 7-10/07/2014

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- “Andrew Gillet: *Envoys and Political Communication in the Late Antique West. Popes and Emperor in Late Antiquity*”
A Reading that Shaped my Research. Università degli studi Roma Tré, Roma, 21/05/2015
- “La papauté dans l’empire byzantin: le pontificat de Vigile et l’affaire des trois chapitres”.
Séminaire de Michel Kaplan, Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, Paris, 28/04/2014

EXPECTED PUBLICATIONS

The *Collectio Canonum Mutinensis* and the Editions of the *Liber Pontificalis*

Le *Liber Pontificalis* et les conciles œcuméniques

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PAULA MANSTETTEN

ESR SOAS

<http://pimic.eu/who/#/paula-manstetten>

PhD: Knowledge and Power in Medieval Syria (mid-10th - mid-12th century). The transmission of learning in a period of institutionalisation

CONFERENCE PAPERS AND SEMINAR TALKS

- British Association for Islamic Studies (BRAIS) The Second Annual Conference of the British Association for Islamic Studies “*The Umayyad Mosque of Damascus as Educational Institution in the Medieval Period*” in the panel “The Transmission, Preservation and Socio-political Use of Knowledge: Historical Figures and Cultural Practices in Diverse Spatial Settings” which was chaired by Prof Hugh Kennedy. April 2015
- International Medieval Congress (IMC) 2015. University of Leeds “Arabic Biographical Dictionaries as Archives of the Scholarly Community?: Ibn ‘Asākir’s History of Damascus” in the panel “Power & Institutions in Medieval Islam & Christendom (PIMIC), I: (Re)Writing the Past - Memory and Political Culture in East and West” which was chaired by Prof Jinty Nelson, Department of History, King’s College London. July 2015
- Society for Medieval Mediterranean conference 2015. University of Lincoln, “Jurists, legal education and politics in 11th -12th century Syria” in the panel “Comparative aspects on the institutionalisation of law - the Mediterranean in the middle ages 2: The Production of Legal Knowledge” which was chaired by Tommi P. Lankila. July 2015
- Annemarie Schimmel Kolleg “Geschichte und Gesellschaft der Mamlukenzeit (1250-1517)”, Universitaet Bonn. Paper at the workshop “The Public Intellectual in the Islamic Middle Periods - Network Perspectives” November 2015

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- The Third Annual Conference of the British Association for Islamic Studies British Association for Islamic Studies (BRAIS) “*Negotiating Power and Authority in 5th-6th/11th-12th Century Syria: Scholars and the Ruling Elites under the Seljūqs and their Successors.*” April 2016
- Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster, Germany. Workshop Caliphs, Sultans, Presidents - Rulers between Religion und Realpolitik throughout Islamic History: “Founders and Beneficiaries of the first *madrasas* in Damascus - Clues to the Religious Policies of the Seljūqs and Būrids (late 11th - mid-12th centuries)”. July 2016
- 50th MESA Annual Meeting” in Boston, Massachusetts. Middle East Studies Association of North Amerika (MESA) “The institutionalization of education in Syria under the Seljuqs and their successors (11th - 12th centuries)”. November 2016

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2. COMMON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES & RESULTS

2.1. PIMIC PANELS AT INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES

LEEDS IMC 2014

PIMIC members actively participated in the 21st International Medieval Congress that took place in Leeds, from 7-10 July 2014. Our partner Michel Kaplan (Paris 1-Panthéon-Sorbonne) organized Session 811 entitled *East Roman and Byzantine Empire and the Papacy, 5th-11th Centuries* and Paul B. Sturtevant, ER at López - Li Films moderated Session 324 *Modern Concepts of Empire and the Medieval World*.

<https://www.leeds.ac.uk/ims/imc/imc2014.html>

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LEEDS IMC 2015

On Tuesday 7th and Wednesday 8th of July 2015, PIMIC sponsored five sessions as part of the Leeds International Medieval Congress. Members of the Board and the Early Stage Researchers presented papers on themes from the PIMIC project, communicating the early results of their research to both the rest of the PIMIC group and the broader community of medieval historians. The themes communicated included the role of memory in political culture; history writing as an institution; hierarchies of power; the institutionalisation of canon law; and the use of violence to institutionalise power. The sessions had each incorporated papers exploring these themes in different geographic areas, in order to highlight the comparative nature of the larger project.

Programme

Session 525 - Tuesday 7th July, 9.00-10.30

Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC), 1:
(Re)Writing the Past - Memory and Political Culture in East and West
Moderator: Dame Janet Nelson

Sarah Greer - Reassessing the Past in the *Primordia* of Hrotsvitha of Gandersheim

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Paula Manstetten - Arabic Biographical Dictionaries as Archives of the Scholarly Community? Ibn 'Asākir's *History of Damascus*
Stuart Airlie - Remembering the Future: Genealogical Authority in the Carolingian World

Session 625 - Tuesday 7th July, 11.15-12.45

Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC), II: Comparative Approaches to Historiography in Medieval Islam and Christendom

Moderator: Attilio Stella

Hugh Kennedy - The Road to Dandanqan: The Historiography of Really Bad Decision Making

Cory Hitt - Transmission of Social Ideals in *L'Histoire de Guillaume de Maréchal*

Ian D. Morris- Ardashir Doesn't Live Here Any More: Persian Theory and Arabian Practice at the Early Islamic Court

Session 725 - Tuesday 7th July 14.15-15.45

Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC), III: Power in Practice - Reproducing and Negotiating Medieval Rulership

Moderator: Hugh Kennedy

Rasmus Bech Olsen - Power and Protest in Mamluk Syria

Ana Rodríguez- Spatiality and the Power of Memory: On Kings and Places in Castile, 12th-13th Centuries

Evgeniya Shelina - Hierarchies among Equals in 13th-Century Christendom

Session 825 - Tuesday 7th July, 16.30-18.00

Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC), IV: Power, Institutions, and Canon Law in Byzantine and Medieval Contexts

Moderator: Tommi Lankila

Adrian Viale - The Institutional Identity of the Papacy and the Lateran Council of 649

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Jack Roskilly - Byzantine Bishops' Canonical Questions in the
12th Century

Jasmin Hauck - Marriage Dispensations from the Diocese of Florence,
1455-1530

*Session 1025 - Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and
Christendom (PIMIC), V: Controlling Violence in the Middle Ages*

Moderator: Jasmin Hauck

Attilio Stella - Vassals, Knights, and Squires: From Local Customs to
Law in 13th-Century Italy

Tommi Lankila - Religion, War, and Law: Islamic Raids in the Central
Mediterranean

Emanuele Conte - Quitting the Feudal Justice: How a Legal Theory
Turned Vassals into Owners - Modena, 1180

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SOCIETY FOR THE MEDIEVAL MEDITERRANEAN 2015

Law, Custom and Ritual in the Medieval Mediterranean (Lincoln, 13-15 July 2015).

Organiser of the panel: Attilio Stella, University of Tel Aviv

Panel 1. *The Making of Political Discourses* (coordinator: Attilio Stella - Tel Aviv University)

Paper a. Adrian Viale (Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne) - Legal Elements in Papal-Imperial Communications (6th-7th Centuries)

Paper b. Evgeniya Shelina (Centro de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales, Madrid) - The Power of Language and the Language of Power in the 13th-Century Castilian Law

Paper c. Rasmus B. Olsen (Birkbeck College, London) - Chronicles as sources for rituals in the early Mamluk period: manifestations of power and protest

Panel 2. *The Production of Legal Knowledge* (coordinator: Tommi P. Lankila - Princeton-Roma Tor Vergata)

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Paper a. Paula Manstetten (SOAS London) - Jurists, legal education and politics in 11th - 12th century Syria

Paper b. Esther-Miriam Wagner (Woolf Institute and University of Cambridge) - Scribal practice and legal record-keeping in the Cairo Genizah

Paper c. Attilio Stella (Tel Aviv University) - Is Feudalism Dead? Rituals, Customs and Laws of Fiefs in Medieval Italy

Panel 3. *Law in Its Social Contexts* (coordinator: Attilio Stella - Tel Aviv University)

Paper a. Tommi P. Lankila (Università di Roma Tor Vergata, Princeton University) - Islamic Law and 'Saracen Raids' in the early medieval Central Mediterranean

Paper b. Bogdan C. Smarandache (University of Toronto) The Ḥanbalī Emigration of 551 AH/1156 AD from the Latin Kingdom of Jerusalem in Light of Legal Opinions on Muslims in Dār al-Ḥarb

Paper c. Jasmin Hauck (Università Roma Tre) - Marriage Dispensations and Marriage Customs in Renaissance Florence (1460-1530).

<http://msrg.blogs.lincoln.ac.uk/events/conference-b-2/society-for-medieval-mediterranean-conference-2015/>

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MESA 2016

50 Years of Scholarship
1966-2016

2016 MESA Annual Meeting, Boston, 17-20 November, 2016

[P4595] Power and Institutions in Times of Transition: Case Studies from the Medieval Middle East

Organised by Paula Manstetten

This panel explored the changing nature of power and institutions during four important periods of political transition in the Medieval Middle East: the 7th-century conquests, the disintegration of the Abbasid caliphate in the early 10th century, the end of Fatimid rule in Syria and concurrent Seljuq takeover in the 11th century, and the establishment of Mamluk rule in Syria in the 13th and 14th centuries. These transitions posed challenges to rulers' legitimacy and the practice of governance. The three papers in this panel explored the ways in which rulers and elites met these challenges, and the historically specific ramifications for the development of social institutions.

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The first paper, lectured by Hugh Kennedy, looked at the development of the term sultan from denoting power or the authorities in general to becoming a title of monarchy referring to a specific individual, thus shedding light on the idea of "the state" during the break-up of the Abbasid caliphate and the rise of the Turkish sultanates.

The third paper, lectured by Paula Manstetten, explored how in the 11th century, the takeover of the Seljuqs in Syria after a century of Fatimid rule prompted an increasing institutionalization of the scholarly communities, modes of patronage, and finally of the social delineations of the Sunni schools of law.

The third paper, lectured by Rasmus Bech Olsen, examined how the Mamluk sultans and their provincial deputies manifested their claims to power in Damascus in the 13th and 14th centuries. It focused on both how the Mamluks modified the built environment through building and infrastructure projects as well as the ways in which their ceremonial practices related to the local urban landscape.

ABSTRACTS:

- ["Sultan" in the tenth century](#) by [Kennedy, Hugh](#)
- [The institutionalization of education in Syria under the Seljuqs and their successors \(11th - 12th centuries\)](#) by [Manstetten,](#)

MEMBERS:

[Jonathan P. Berkey](#)

(Davidson College)

Panel Participating Role(s):
Chair;

[Hugh Kennedy](#)

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[Paula](#)

(SOAS University of London)

- [The Sultan and the City: The topography of power in Mamluk Damascus 1250 - 1400](#) by [Olsen, Rasmus Bech](#)

Panel Participating Role(s):
Presenter;

[Zayde G. Antrim](#)

(Trinity College)

Panel Participating Role(s):
Discussant;

[Paula Manstetten](#)

(SOAS, University of London)

Panel Participating Role(s):
Organizer; Presenter;

[Rasmus Bech Olsen](#)

(Birkbeck College, University of London)

Panel Participating Role(s):
Presenter;

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2.2 PUBLICATIONS

As explained in the preliminary paragraph of this report, the main challenge of the team consists in providing possible answers to this problematic question, avoiding conceptual bypasses, evolutionary or teleological models, simplistic oppositions and dyadic narratives (East/West, Christendom/Islam, etc.) biases which often underlie traditional historiographies and socio-institutional approaches. Eduardo Manzano's article [Why Did Islamic Medieval Institutions Become so Different from Western Medieval Institutions?](#) in the Open Access journal *Medieval Worlds*, edited by Walter Pohl and André Gringrich is probably the most representative result of PIMIC in terms to our approach to the comparative research. All members of the Board, as it is indicated in the article itself, have contributed with their discussions and ideas to the preparation of this article.

A first set of questions around which the PIMIC programme is advancing has been outlined in the volume *Diverging paths?* by the members of the PIMIC ITN board. The authors draw at least four clear areas of research: A methodological one, (de)constructing the concept of institution itself; legal institutions and the codification of law; economic institutions and state funding strategies; self-representation of power institutions and their physical embodiments.

HUDSON, John and RODRÍGUEZ, Ana, (eds) *Diverging Paths? The Shapes of Power and Institutions in Mediaeval Christendom and Islam* (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2014). <http://www.brill.com/products/book/diverging-paths>

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Last but not least, **an ongoing volume is being prepared by the PIMIC fellows**, result of their previous collaboration and work in common presenting panels and conferences, on the one hand, and of their training on academic impact, on the other (Publishing School for Historians I and II):

Publisher: Kate Hammond at Brill Medieval History Editor has expressed provisional interest pending submission of a full proposal.

Proposed title: Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom

Editors: Cory Hitt and Adrian Viale

Contributors:

Adrian Viale, Sarah Greer, Evgeniya Shelina, Attilio Stella, Paula Manstetten, Tommi Lankila, Cory Hitt, and Ian Morris

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3. INDIVIDUAL CONTRIBUTIONS (MEMBERS OF THE BOARD)

ALGAZI, Gadi, *The Making a Scholarly Way of Life, 1480-1630*, Oxford University Press, 2017 (In print)

ALGAZI, Gadi, “Forget Memory: Some Critical Remarks on Memory, Forgetting and History” , in *Damnatio in Memoria: Deformation und Gegenkonstruktionen von Geschichte* , Sebastian Scholz, Gerald Schwedler, and Kai-Michael Sprenger, eds. (Vienna/Cologne/Weimer: Böhlau, 2014), pp. 25-34

CAROCCI, Sandro, German translation of S. Carocci, S. Collavini, “The Cost of States. Politics and Exactions in the Christian West (Sixth to Fifteenth Centuries)”, in *Diverging Paths? The Shapes of Power and Institutions in Medieval Christendom and Islam*, ed. by John Hudson and Ana Rodríguez, Brill, Leiden, 2014, pp. 125-158: “Der Preis des Staates Politik und Abgaben im mittelalterlichen Europa (6.-14. Jahrhundert)”, in *Annali dell’Istituto storico italo-germanico in Trento / Jahrbuch des italienisch-deutschen historischen Instituts in Trient*, 41, 2015 / 2, pp. 77-116

CAROCCI, Sandro, *Signorie di Mezzogiorno, Società rurali, poteri aristocratici e monarchia (XII-XIII secolo)*, Roma, Viella, 2014, pp. 596 (and its English translation, forthcoming)

CONTE, Emanuele, *La fuerza del texto. Casuística y categorías del derecho medieval*, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, 2016

HUDSON, John, 2013 University of Michigan Law School: “Maitland, Austin, and Maine”

HUDSON, John, British Legal History Conference (Glasgow): “Maitland and Austin: Legal history and legal thought in the late nineteenth century” (plenary lecture), 2013

HUDSON, John, Allen Brown Memorial Lecture on Anglo-Norman Studies: “From the Articles of the Barons to Magna Carta” 2015

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HUDSON, John, International Medieval Congress, Leeds: "Frustration leads to anger: clerics and laymen in the courtroom", 2015

HUDSON, John, The Magna Carta Conference (London): "Magna Carta: *ius commune* and Common Law" (roundtable), 2015

HUDSON, John and CRUMPLIN, Sally (eds.), *The Making of Europe. Essays in Honor of Robert Bartlett*, (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2016)

HUDSON, John, "England and *The Making of Europe*: Conquest, Colonization and Cultural Change", in John Hudson and Sally Crumplin (eds.), *The Making of Europe. Essays in Honor of Robert Bartlett*, (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2016) pp. 33.52

HUDSON, John, ed. with G. S. Garnett, *J. C. Holt, Magna Carta, (3rd edition, with new Introduction and other additional material*, Cambridge, 2015)

HUDSON, John, ed. with S. Baxter, P. Wormald, *Papers Preparatory to The Making of English Law volume ii*, (2014):

<http://www.earlyenglishlaws.ac.uk/reference/wormald/>

HUDSON, John, C. Warren Hollister Memorial Lecture; "The place of the reign of Henry I in English legal history", 2015

HUMFRESS, Caroline, "Ordering Divine Knowledge in Late Roman Legal Discourse" *Collegium. Studies across Discipline in the Humanities and Social Sciences*, forthcoming (Helsinki: accepted for publication)

HUMFRESS, Caroline, Joint Committee for Nordic Research Councils in the Humanities and the Social Sciences (NOS-HS) & the Academy of Finland project "Political Power in the Early Modern European and Islamic Worlds". International Conference: "Eurasian Empires, Public Space/Sphere, and Collective Identities at the Threshold of Modernity". Closing Address. December 2015

<https://www.jyu.fi/ytk/laitokset/yfi/en/research/projects/political-institutions/political-power-in-the-early-modern-european-and-islamic-worlds>

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HUMFRESS, Caroline, Centre for Advanced Studies, Oslo, international conference "Donations and Inheritance". Opening keynote paper: "Gift-giving and Inheritance Strategies in Late Roman Law and Legal Practice (Third to Sixth Centuries CE)" January 2015

HUMFRESS, Caroline, Oxford University and Maison Française, Oxford. International conference "Legal Pluralism in the Roman Empire". Opening keynote paper: "Rethinking Forum Shopping in the Context of Ancient Law" June 2015.

HUMFRESS, Caroline, LMU-Munich, international colloquium "Natural Law in Ancient Philosophy". Invited paper: "Natural Law and the 'Hypothetical Case' in Roman Juristic Writings" November 2014

HUMFRESS, Caroline, "Telling Stories about (Roman) Law: Rules and Concepts in Legal Discourse" in Dresch, P. and Scheele, J., *Legalism: Rules and Categories* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2015): 79-104

<https://global.oup.com/academic/product/legalism-9780198753810?cc=gb&lang=en&>

KENNEDY, Hugh, *Caliphate. The History of an Idea*, Penguin, London, 2016

KENNEDY, Hugh, "Landed Property and Government Finance in the Early 'Abbasid Caliphate'", in John Hudson and Sally Crumplin (eds.), *The Making of Europe. Essays in Honor of Robert Bartlett*, (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2016) pp. 264-276

MANZANO, Eduardo, "Power and Institution in Medieval Islam and Christendom," on Tuesday, November 22, 2016, University of Chicago

MANZANO, Eduardo, "From Qurṭuba to Córdoba" Discussion with Pfr. Abdulhadi Al Ajmi, Director of the History Department. Faculty of Letters. Kuwait University, *Dar al-Athar al-Islamiyya*, Kuwait, 29th November, 2015.

MANZANO, Eduardo, "The Umayyad Caliphate in al-Andalus", Tehran Qasr Museum, Spanish Embassy at the Islamic Republic of Iran, Tehran, 30th July 2015

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MANZANO, Eduardo, University of Oxford Centre for Socio-Legal Studies. St. John's College in Legalism seminar series 3rd of March, 2015 "Why were Islamic medieval institutions so different from Western medieval institutions?"

MANZANO, Eduardo, "How Hispania became al-Andalus. Social change in the aftermath of the Arab conquest", The Graduate Center, CUNY, New York, November, 2014

MANZANO, Eduardo, "De cómo los árabes realmente invadieron *Hispania*", *al-Qanṭara*, 35, 1, 2014, p. 311-319.

MANZANO, Eduardo, "Conquest and Settlement. What al-Andalus can tell us about the Arab expansion at the time of the Umayyad Caliphate", in A. Marsham *Early Umayyad Caliphate*, Rothledge (forthcoming)

MANZANO, Eduardo. « Circulation des biens et richesses entre al-Andalus et l'Occident européen aux VIIIe -Xe siècles ». L. Feller et A. Rodríguez eds. *Objets sous contrainte. Circulation des richesses et valeur des choses au Moyen Âge*. pp. 147 - 180. Publications de la Sorbonne, 2013.

RODRIGUEZ, Ana, "Poder e Instituciones en la Cristiandad y en el Islam en la Edad Media. Un proyecto de investigación, formación y divulgación en historia comparada", *Del dato a la interpretación histórica. Una mirada interdisciplinar desde el medievalismo*, University of the Basque Country, Vitoria, 13th December 2013

RODRIGUEZ, Ana, "Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom", *CARMEN. The Worldwide Medieval Network Annual Meeting*, University of Sarajevo, 12th September 2015

RODRÍGUEZ, Ana, with John Hudson (ed.), *Diverging Paths? The Shapes of Power and Institutions in Mediaeval Christendom and Islam* (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2014).

RODRÍGUEZ, Ana, with Laurent Feller (dirs.), *Expertise et valeur des choses au Moyen Âge. Savoirs, écritures, pratiques* (Madrid, Casa de Velazquez 2016).

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

RODRÍGUEZ, Ana, with Laurent Feller (dirs.) *Circulation des richesses et valeur des choses au Moyen Âge*. (Publications de la Sorbonne, 2013)´.

RODRÍGUEZ, Ana, “Narratives of Expansion, Last Wills, Poor Expectations and the Conquest of Seville (1248)” in John Hudson and Sally Crumplin (eds.), *The Making of Europe. Essays in Honor of Robert Bartlett*, (Leiden, Brill Publishers, 2016), pp. 123-142.

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TRAINING WORKSHOPS

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

PIMIC Project aimed to create a new generation of PhD fellows, qualified to develop their scholarly work from groundbreaking perspectives and by means of a comparative approach, but also equipped to respond to new social, political and cultural challenges. PIMIC PhD's are now trained to be able to communicate their results to a wide array of audiences.

How it has been done:

By insisting on a comparative element within the individual research topics.

By developing ideas within a collaborative as well as comparative scheme.
By emphasizing communication, integrating work with Private Sector partners.

Therefore, training has been essential, and the quality of the programme has been consequently the main concern of the project. On the one hand, the coordination of a wide-range of scholarly works at pre and post-doctoral level has articulated a common research programme. On the other hand, PIMIC has assured the best possible academic supervision and scholarly training in both their host institution and through the network of scholars provided. In addition, PIMIC project has developed the most innovative network training for both Early Stage Researchers (ESR) and Experienced Researchers (ER) by using multidisciplinary and intersectional techniques. Network training program has been articulated through a programme of training workshops and secondments.

<http://pimic.eu/how/>

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Sources in Context

St Andrews 28-30 Oct. 2013

On 28-30 October 2013 the University of St Andrews hosted the opening workshop of the PIMIC ITN. Scholars and postgraduate students from Europe, Israel, and North America met for a training course on Sources and Source Criticism, held in the University's Parliament Hall. Present were the Partners, the Fellows, and various associated scholars.

Sessions were held on Record Sources (led by Tim Greenwood and John Hudson); Narrative Sources (Robert Bartlett and Eduardo Manzano); Archaeology (Hugh Kennedy and Alessandra Molinari); Lawbooks (Magnus Ryan and Bernard Stolte); and Literary Sources (Gadi Algazi and Steve White). The Project's postgraduate students (from New Zealand, Argentina, Russia, Finland, the U.S., U.K., Germany, and Italy) also presented outlines of their PhDs and introduced a discussion of notions of Institutionalisation. Collaborative working methods were developed amongst the participants in the project. Fellows met with administrators, a Supervisory Board meeting was held, and a workshop on PhD writing was given (Roberta Cimino and Kate Gilbert).

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Legal And Social Issues In Context

Rome 2014

The PIMIC conference in Rome dealt with the matters of legal and social studies, and how to unite these different fields together. The conference brought together various specialists from several universities around the world to vivify the conversation and present different ways to approach these issues. Thanks to the conference's wide attendance, the debate covered nearly a millennium of medieval history with varying topics, such as the Viking kingdoms, the Lombard Italy, Fredrick II, papal penitentiaries, and villages near high medieval Verona.

The conference opened with Stephen White's talk about Conflict, Law and 'Dispute-Processing'. The entering talk thereby brought up a third source-type besides those legal or social: Literary sources turned out to be innovative sources for the study of legal and social questions. This paper was followed by Emanuel Conte's (legal historian) and Sandro Carocci's (social historian) joint presentation (Legal and Social Aspects in Context: Serfdom) of legal documents from the period of Frederick II (1194-1250). A special institution and its referring sources were thereby investigated as a legal and a social institution alike. The talk by Massimo Valerani investigated the topic of Strategies of litigation without legal rules? The myth of settlement of conflicts "as social institution" on the meta-level of historiographical shifts and their ideological groundwork determined by their Zeitgeist and academic positions. Sara Menzinger focused on the learned discourse of a specific aspect of medieval cities' administration: Fiscal theories in the Italian communal cities of the 12th century: a debate with Late Antiquity. Again, Caroline Humfress focused on the connection of legal and social history on a broader scale, combining close reading of late antique source material with pondering the usage of contemporary social and legal theories for writing medieval history (Law in Society? Thinking through texts and contexts).

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While open discussions followed the presentations of the professors, four of the PhD students (early stage researchers = ESRs) profited from a possibility to present parts of their research under the heading of “legal and social history.” They received comments from two discussants, those of a PhD student followed by those of an experienced researcher/professor on their topic, Evgeniya Shelina presented impressions from her research on The Norwegian concept(s) of Power and its (their) terminology. She highlighted the process of translation between the Latin and the vernacular power terminology focusing on the translation of the term *regnum*. Tommi Lankila presented a paper on Saracen mentions in the chartulae of Cava de' Tirreni, which explored legal material dealing with Saracens from the archive of Cava de' Tirreni and how to use such material for the social study of the region of Salerno. Jasmin Hauck gave a talk on The social representation of legal knowledge: *Scientia* and *ignorantia* in the registers of the papal penitentiary. Starting from the terminology of knowledge in her sources, she shed light on the medieval lawyers' ambiguous relation towards antique legal texts as an authoritative reference and their awareness of a changed social reference framework. Attilio Stella aimed at connecting kinship analysis and conflict settlement in the legal arena. He presented family networks as an explanation for the course of legal procedures between diverse institutions. The Settlement of Disputes in High Medieval Manors. A Case Study from Northern Italy.

Besides the official part of the conference, a guided library visit to the Senate Library was introduced as both a rich fundus of legal sources and an institution that has grown in the atmosphere of the Italian national movement, being itself an interesting object of the entanglement of legal and social history. One evening session was dedicated to the presentation of administrative issues by Laura Rodríguez and Paul Sturtevant, such as the ESRs Presentations on the International Medieval Congress in Leeds (2015) and the Introduction of the Media School.

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The Roman conference was an excellent avenue for the ESRs to widen their perspective settling sources between legal and social models of interpretations. A fundamental concept was the mixture of advanced researchers' broader-view presentations compared to the more focused presentations of the ESRs. The modes of the ESR presentation and discussing were active ways of creating focused works parting from this heuristic twofold-model. The expert and open discussion session was giving feedback to their works and developing towards more general questions linking the medieval Islam and Christendom.

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Complementary Skills

St Andrews 2014

In June 2014, the University of St Andrews hosted a PIMIC workshop focused on the dissemination of academic research through new media. The workshop featured a variety of practical sessions as well as presentations on the various methods of communication with the public. University of Glasgow Prof. Stuart Airlie offered an academic's perspective in his paper "Percy Ernst Schramm goes to the movies: Aspects of Medieval Modernity". Lopez-Li Films, one of the PIMIC private partners, spoke about documentary production and how to bridge the gap between the filmmaking industry and academics. David Hendy gave a fascinating presentation, titled "Doing History on the Radio", that explored the process of pitching, writing, and producing a BBC radio serial.

A great deal of time was devoted to instructing the Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) on the practical skills needed to engage with new media. Dave Musgrove, from BBC History Magazine, spoke about the elements of a successful history podcast. Andy Eccles, IT officer at the School of History, provided hands-on instruction in podcast-recording software, and University of St Andrews lecturers also instructed the ESRs on blogging and creating a web presence. Greg Hitt, VP of Corporate Communications at Walmart, finished off the workshop with a session about communicating with journalists and politicians.

The opportunity to engage in practical sessions and learn about the broader communication of research provided the ESRs with a useful set of skills to use in their future academic professions. This workshop, with its presentation of the many and varied ways to engage with the wider public, provided a valuable reminder of the importance, opportunity and rewards of disseminating new historical research widely outside of academia.

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Publishing School for Historians, I

20-21 October, 2014

Over two days, Brill academic publishers hosted PIMIC at a ‘Publishing school for historians.’ The workshop aimed to introduce the students to the world of academic publishing, providing them with practical knowledge and endowing them with the skills and understanding necessary to promote positive relationships between scholars and publishers. It is hoped that, by familiarising the students at this early stage, they will be better informed when they come to interact with publishers and will have a clear understanding of the processes and issues involved, from the publishing perspective as well as from the author’s perspective.

The workshop sessions focused on four different publishing products: books and book series, reference works (including online), journals, and primary sources (including digitisation). The workshop participants were first introduced to the product by a Brill editor, with the process of setting up such a product, and the issues and considerations from the publishing perspective outlined. The participants then broke into two groups to work on a series of case studies. These aimed to encourage the participants to ‘think like a publisher’, using a sample proposal as the basis; the students were asked to discuss and critique the proposal, taking into account issues such as logistical requirements, financial considerations, academic content, likely audience and market, and opportunities for further development. These sessions were felt to be useful; the students came away well-informed and with a more rounded view of the academic publishing process, and the sessions also gave rise to some interesting discussion of bigger issues in publishing today, such as possible future online developments, the Open Access movement, and the changing role of publishers in academia.

We also enjoyed two excursions as part of the workshop. As a complement to the session on primary sources and digitisation, we were hosted by Leiden University library, where we learnt about the history of the Vossiani

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Latini collection of manuscripts (currently being digitised by Brill), were able to view some of the highlight manuscripts, and heard about procedures of digitisation within the library. A highlight of the workshop was the excursion to Printforce: a print-on-demand factory which prints around 10,000 unique books per day. After a talk on the history of printing and some information about the company, we were given a fascinating guided tour of the factory at work, with all the automated machines explained and the processes demonstrated for our benefit: from the printing of the innerworks, the binding and the production of the hardcovers, all the way through to shipping and postage. The efficiency of the operation was very impressive.

The workshop was rounded off by a plenary session, with talks given by two publishers from outside Brill. Simon Forde (formerly Brepols, now Amsterdam University Press) took commercial publishing as his topic, and drew attention to the sorts of issues that first-time authors should consider when submitting manuscripts for publication; several of the students commented that they had never considered how important issues such as brand recognition, pricing structure, and editorial relationships were with regard to academic publishers. Anniek Meinders (Leiden University Press) then gave an interesting insight into the challenges and opportunities of setting up a publishing list in a recently-established university press.

Overall, the workshop offered something different to the previous more academic PIMIC gatherings; although perhaps not as immediately, obviously relevant to the early stage researchers as a more traditional academic conference, the workshop provided them with a solid grounding in academic publishing, an area which initially can be confusing, which should stand them in extremely good stead for the future.

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Media School for Historians I

Madrid, December 1-12, 2014

The Media School has been an extraordinary experience, not only for the twelve ITN Fellows that took part in it, but also for the lecturers involved: results have been “astonishing”. The school ultimately aimed to provide trainees with practical knowledge, focusing on the requirements of the audiovisual industry and the needs and expectations of a challenging target audience increasingly interested in historical knowledge. For this reason, the first installment of the course can be considered a success. This first installment of the course can be considered a “useful success”.

On Monday, December 1, the Fellows met at the Centro de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales - CSIC of Madrid, equipped with tech-material and curious about what they what they would discover in the following days.

Film Producer Antonio Saura Medrano gave the first lecture at 10 a.m., aiming to solve the ITN Fellows´ most basic doubts and questions: what to work on to December 12 and how to use the camera.

Following his answers was a 20-minute presentation entitled “Documentary and Society”. Here, A. Saura guided the audience through the controversial idea that it is not possible to maintain objectivity while making a documentary. Taking advantage of this first attitude ITN fellows were invited to share their plans for the media project by writing a sketch for the following day.

After lunch, Filmmaker Gonzalo Ballester began his sessions, helping the participants set up the camera to better understand different recording options.

During the second day of the course, A. Saura decided to start dealing with “writing issues” concerning movie making. Therefore, on January 2 he told the ITN Fellows about “How to Write a Documentary”.

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Prior to any work a filmmaker must ask himself: “who is going to be my primary target?” because according to A. Saura, screenwriting is all about finding a voice.

Once the main opinions were provided and some screening examples were given, the students began to discuss their suggestions with the professor. Some wanted to know the risk of making the first act of a documentary “too long”, while others proposed the idea that not every documentary must necessarily have a moral or political position of its own.

The end of the day held remarkable participation of the ITN Fellows once the screening of some pieces of Medieval and non Medieval History documentaries was made. The Fellows wanted to know how to start shooting, and when to decide between a short, quick shot and a long, slow one. Professor Antonio Saura gave a wide array of examples from interviews in order to demonstrate the smart choice while shooting testimonies.

Professor Gonzalo Ballester closed the journey by providing a useful clip on the most basic camera shots they could start with and a feasible “setting-up” exercise to better handle with the cameras and micros. All the students were invited to create their own shotlists prior to the first day of recording.

Little did they know on day three, the amount of information suggested for progression was immense: once the students sent the lecturers their abstracts, they were all carefully double-checked and questioned. It was going to be the first day on “Editing Workshop” and everyone was excited.

Professor Sara Azcona, a computer engineer with plenty of professional film editing experience, opened the workshop clear about detail: editors must be careful when saving documents and creating folders. Everyone got the message.

A number of hours followed with doubts, errors, mistakes and questions that first day in the Editing workshop. Then, on the fourth day of the course, Professor Carlos Saura Medrano came to join the group and helped

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participants with their doubts. The three instructors guided the ITN group, patiently attending to their suggestions. They would have never believed the amazing results they would receive at the end of the week.

That fourth day was also marked by Antonio Saura's morning session dedicated to the process of "Watching Documentaries," and to the composition of the shots when shooting the film.

After the three-day-weekend (following the Mid-Term review on Friday the 5th), the ITN Fellows had recorded enough audiovisual material to use during the last week of the course. Each day was divided into different "Editing Workshop" sessions in the morning and pitching arrangements during the afternoon.

The hard working ITN group was invited to take a guided tour through the CCHS Library on Tuesday at midday. The Archives were opened for them. Drawn through the peculiar corridors of the building, they were prompted to ask for more details regarding the periodic publications and digital documents available.

The Final Pitch Session came on Friday the 12th. The students exposed their works during a 10-minute presentation and screening of each clip. Each gave the audience a positive surprise, particularly in regard to the careful music selection. Every three-minute Historic clip received a deserved ovation and the lecturers, headed by Director José Luis López-Linares, provided feedback and suggestions for the students' following work.

The group was summoned for the Second Installment of the Media School for Historians, in April 2015.

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Media School for Historians II

Madrid, April 20-30, 2015

Committed to the general idea of delivering a short piece of documentary and understanding the “life of a movie”, the ITN fellows worked hard on their subjects and their translation to the screen.

The “Media School for Historians 1” provided an introduction to video creation, through script writing, recording, editing and pitching. The twelve ITN Fellows had all developed an interesting product from scratch, which later became a trailer of what would be their future documentary. Now, four months later, they confronted a new challenge: To work on their footage and “sell” a definitive 10-minute documentary to an ideal prospective buyer.

It was not easy: In just two weeks, the ITN fellows focused on editing while attending to new paths in their academic lives, the “Oral communication strategy” and the “Website positioning workshop.”

As the proverb says, “no pain, no gain,” and after the first week, many students experienced plenty of pain working on their clips.

The first Thursday was a sort of meeting point for the CCHS CORPI Project members and PIMIC Fellows: Professor Eduardo Manzano brought them together to give a paper on contrasted Islamic and Western Medieval Institutions. The morning happened to be full of useful information for Medievalist researchers. It was followed by a thematic lunch, where people shared opinions and perspectives over the relationship between law and politics while coexisting with religion, both in West and Islam cultures.

One of the main characteristics of this second course has been the variety of participants on each session. Spanish Film Academy Award winner Ruth Gabriel conducted a workshop that helped the ITN fellows properly present their research subjects; through four sessions recording sessions, the

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students gave their discourses, and afterwards, received edited clips to fix their mistakes in the future.

Meanwhile, the Marketing Online specialist, Miguel Cuesta, provided a wide array of techniques to work with audiovisual material uploaded to Internet. Working in six groups, the students watched a sample minute-long video clip and learned how to apply some SEO techniques to find visits to a particular website and be positioned first on top of the list.

The students worked under considerable pressure, but still managed to deliver an excellent, short documentary clip during the last Thursday, on April 30. This was thanks to the speeches by Jon Andi3n (Head of Business & legal Affairs at Morena Films) and Antonio Saura (C.E.O. Latido Films) who shared their experiences as a lawyer and a producer in the film industry, respectively.

All were nervous on pitching day; teachers and students were seated, the camera recording their surprisingly confident speeches. After the presentation of their work, Jos3 Luis L3pez-Linares, Ruth Gabriel and Antonio Saura commented with their impressions and gave some advice for future projects.

Two examples of the results:

[Sara Greer: Born to Rule, Mathilda of Quedlinburg](#)

[Adri3n Viale: Ancient Popes](#)

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Publishing School for Historians, II

Leeds, 10 July, 2015

Over one morning at the end of the International Medieval Congress at the University of Leeds, Brill and PIMIC hosted the second iteration of the ‘Publishing School for Historians.’ Entitled ‘An Introduction to Academic Publishing’, the workshop aimed to demystify the world of academic publishing by offering the students practical advice on different forms of publishing, from both medievalist scholars and editors working in academic history publishing.

As well as the eleven PIMIC fellows, the workshop was also opened up to non-PIMIC participants, and was advertised as part of the IMC’s programme; interest was high, and the available spaces were allocated extremely quickly. The workshop was also covered and followed on social media; full details available here: <https://storify.com/kрмаude/academic-publishing-workshop-imc2015#publicize>

The workshop comprised three sessions. The first focused on writing a book proposal and turning the thesis into a monograph, and was led by Alaric Hall (University of Leeds). The session began with an individual task - writing a mock book proposal in 20 minutes - before Alaric gave a talk based on his own experiences, and feedback from the book proposal task and a question and answer session rounded off the session. The second session focused on publishing a journal article, led by Katy Cubitt (University of York). Katy began the session with a journals brainstorm, before delivering a talk full of useful advice on the subject, followed by Marti Huetink (Brill) offering the publishers’ perspective. The third session looked at putting together an edited volume, led by Jonathan Jarrett (University of Birmingham), comprising interesting talks by Jonathan (academic perspective) and Simon Forde (Amsterdam University Press / Medieval Institute Publications), on the publishers’ perspective, before a general question and discussion session, and conclusions by Ana Rodriguez, rounded off the workshop.

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The workshop was praised by attendees, and the reaction on social media was particularly positive. Hopefully the workshop provided the participants with a solid knowledge-base for future academic publishing ventures, some useful tips and tricks specific to publishing in medieval studies, and also an awareness that academic publishing is, at the moment, an ever changing field - with new possibilities but also new problems abounding, there is not necessarily a consensus yet on best practice.

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PIMIC Achievements

Madrid February 2016

During the months of February-March 2016 most of the PIMIC fellows spent their secondment in Madrid. As part of their training they learned how to curate an exhibition, from how to develop the idea and write the statement to the production work (design, search for material, transport, location, etc.). The result of this collaborative work has been the exhibition *The Way We Are Ruled. Exhibiting Invisible Institutions*, which was first displayed within the context of the PIMIC Final Forum, London 24th-26th June 2016.

On March, 3rd 2016, the fellows received an intensive course on funding opportunities for researchers in the field of Humanities and Social Sciences, lectured by experienced D&R project managers of the CCHS-CSIC and participated as well in a round table with Dr. Therese Martin, Tenured Scientist of the Instituto de Historia CCHS-CSIC, IP of the Starting Grant [MEFECIT](#) *Reassessing the Roles of Women as 'Makers' of Medieval Art and Architecture*, and Dr. Jan Thiele, Marie Curie Fellow at the ILC-CCHS-CSIC around the topic "how to write a winning grant application".

During their secondment period in Madrid, and as part of the PIMIC Achievements training course, the fellows attended the PIMIC Seminar Series, having the opportunity to meet, listen and create a research network with young medievalists who have accomplished their doctoral theses in a framework of methodological and / or technological innovation.

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SEMINARS

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CCHS-CSIC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 316732

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVEAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

Seminar: **Conveniencia and Physics of Scale: Ethno-Religious Relations in Medieval Spain and the Mediterranean**, Brian Catlos,
Associate Professor & Director of Undergraduate Studies of Religious Studies,
University of Colorado at Boulder, 6th June 2013

CCHS-CSIC International Symposium “**Memory as Clout: By, For, and About Medieval Women**”

This symposium taked on the topic of memory as an instrument of power. Women’s roles in memoria and commemoration have been well studied by scholars of the Middle Ages; indeed, they are a central theme in the historiography of medieval woman. However, memory has almost always been framed in terms of religion and piety. Here, the papers presented teased out the various functions of remembrance, adding a new layer to traditional concerns with family and spirituality. They analyzed the multiple ways in which memory in the Middle Ages could be wielded to enhance a woman’s power. Employing evidence draw from both written and visual sources, the participants in this symposium opened new perspectives on the significance of memory, recognizing its multiple contributions to medieval women’s clout.

Organized by: Therese Martin (IH, CCHS-CSIC) and Ana Rodríguez (IH, CCHS-CSIC).

Sponsored by Reassessing the Roles of Women as ‘Makers’ of Medieval Art and Architecture (ERC Starting Grant no. 263036), Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC, Marie Curie-ITN no. 316732), Instituto de Historia (CCHS-CSIC) and MEDhis (CCHS-CSIC). 15th November 2013

Seminar: **Everyone but you is stupid! Assessing the Assessments of Public Historical Knowledge**, Paul Sturtevant (PIMIC Experienced Researcher López Li Films, Madrid) 23rd January 2014

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

Seminar: “El ejercicio de la autoridad política en Bizancio (s XIV-XV)
¿Decadencia del sistema imperial o crisis bajomedieval?” Dr. Raúl Estangui,
CNRS- Centre de Recherche d’Histoire et Civilisation de Byzance will lecture a
seminar at the CCHS-CSIC on the exercise of political authority in Byzantium
during the late 14th-15th centuries. 3th April 2014

Seminar: **Healthscaping Medieval Cities: From Theory to Practice**, Guy
Geltner. Professor of Medieval History. Director, Center for Medieval Studies,
University of Amsterdam, 9th September 2014, 12.00 hrs

Seminar: **Papers in Disputes: Petitions to the Crown and the Circulation of
Royal Letters in Late Medieval Castilian Towns**, Yanay Israeli, University of
Michigan, 30th June 2015

Anthony Grafton - David Ruderman, “**Cross-Cultural Dialogues in Early
Modern Europe**”

“A dialogue between longstanding friends and colleagues; a dialogue with
antiquity in the spirit of “Reinassence”; a dialogue between contemporary
readers and pre-modern texts; and, finally, a dialogue between Christians and
Jews in early modern Europe”.

Thursday, 19th June 2015, 4.00 pm. Organized by the projects: PIMIC and
CORPI

Seminar: **Family, Habits and Institutions: Christian, Jewish and Muslim
Scholars from a Comparative Perspective**, Prof. Gadi Algazi, University of
Tel Aviv, 14th September 2016

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PIMIC seminar series

28th January
Attilio Stela, PIMIC fellow, University of Tel Aviv
Orality vs. Literacy? Social Practice, Feudal Lawyers and the Problem of Normativity in the 13th-Century Italy and France

11th February
Roger L. Martínez-Dávila, UCM CONEX-Marie Curie Fellow, Instituto de Historia Julio Caro Baroja, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Global Citizen Scholars: Crowdsourcing Discovery and Manuscript Transcription Via Massive Open Online Courses

18th February
Graham Barrett, Oxford University
The Written and the World in Early Medieval Iberia

25th February
Nicolas Perreux, Frankfurt Universität
European History of the Middle Ages in a Digital Area? Some experiences about Charter Databases, Churches and Historical Semantics

3rd March
Paul Stephenson, University of Lincoln
The Serpent Column: A Cultural Biography

10th March
Jitske Jasperse, Instituto de Historia, CCHS-CSIC
Let's Talk About Sex: A Gendered Approach to Seals and Coins

Roberta Cimino, Leverhulme Early Career Fellow, Department of History, University of Nottingham
Royal Authority, Land and Women's Power in Northern Italy (8th-9th centuries)

14th March
Karen Stöber, Universidad de Lérida
"Not so Far from the Concourse of Men: Religious Houses and Urban Spaces in Medieval Catalonia"

Seminar Room Juan Cabré, 12.00 hrs
Centro de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales-CSIC
C/ Albasanz 26-28, 28037 Madrid

PIMIC SEMINAR SERIES

28th January 2016

Attilio Stela, PIMIC fellow, University of Tel Aviv

Orality vs. Literacy? Social Practice, Feudal Lawyers and the Problem of Normativity in the 13th-Century Italy and France

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVEAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

11th February 2016

Roger Martínez Davila, Roger L. Martínez-Dávila, UC3M CONEX-Marie Curie Fellow, Instituto de Histografía Julio Caro Baroja, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

Global Citizen Scholars: Crowdsourcing Discovery and Manuscript Transcription Via Massive Open Online Courses

18 February 2016

Graham Barrett, Oxford University

The Written and the World in Early Medieval Iberia

25th February 2016

Nicolas Perreux, Francfort Universitat

European History of the Middle Ages in a Digital Area? Some experiences about Charter Databases, Churches and Historical Semantics

10th March 2016

Jitske Jasperse, Instituto de Historia, CCHS-CSIC, *Let's Talk about Sex: A Gendered Approach to Seals and Coins*

Roberta Cimino, Leverhulme Early Career Fellow, Department of History University of Nottingham, *Royal authority, land and women's power in northern Italy (8th-9th centuries)*

14th March 2016

Karen Stöber, Universidad de Lérida

"Not so far from the concourse of men: Religious houses and urban spaces in medieval Catalonia" ?

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 316732

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meanings
symposium

The ARC Centre of Excellence for the History of Emotions (Europe 1100 - 1800) and the Centre for Mediaeval and Early Modern Law and Literature, University of St Andrews present:

EMOTIONS IN THE COURTROOM

Image: Unknown, c.1300, Initial N: King James I of Aragon Overseeing a Court of Law. © J. Paul Getty Trust.

Date: 3-4 May 2015

Location: University of St Andrews
Department of Mediaeval History, St John's House
71 South Street, St Andrews
KY16 9QW, United Kingdom

SPEAKERS:

Professor Stephen D. White (*Emory University*)
 Professor William I. Miller (*University of Michigan*)
 Professor Hans Jacob Orning (*University of Oslo*)
 Dr Susanne Pohl-Zucker (*Independent researcher*)
 Elizabeth Papp Kamali (*University of Michigan*)
 Dr Merridee Bailey (*The University of Adelaide*)
 Dr Ian Forrest (*Oriel College, University of Oxford*)
 Dr Seb Coxon (*University College, London*)
 Professor John Hudson (*University of St Andrews*)

For more information, including abstracts, visit
www.historyofemotions.org.au/events

FOCUS:

The recent surge of interest in the history of emotions has seen medievalists uncover a broad range of new source material recording the affective lives of Europeans in the Middle Ages. A parallel growth of interest in crime and judicial records from ecclesiastical and secular courts has identified these as excellent sources and made clear that the courtroom could be a locus for emotionally charged events. This 1.5 day interdisciplinary symposium brings together scholars of law, literature and history to examine the role that emotions played in legal conduct and procedure.

REGISTRATION

The symposium is free of charge but pre-booking is required before **25th April, 2015**. For pre-booking and information, contact: kimberley.knight@sydney.edu.au

ALL WELCOME!

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

Emotions in the Courtroom, University of St Andrews, Scotland

On 3rd-4th May 2014, a one and half day symposium on the theme of Emotions in the Courtroom was held at the University of St Andrews, Scotland. The symposium was a joint venture between the ARC Centre for the History of Emotions (CHE); The Centre for Mediaeval and Early Modern Law and Literature at the University of St Andrews (CMEML) and the Marie Curie ITN Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom (PIMIC). Funding was also received from the Royal Society of Edinburgh (RSE). The symposium was co-convened by Kimberley Knight (CHE, The University of Sydney), John Hudson (University of St Andrews) and Jamie Page (University of Durham). Present from PIMIC were John Hudson, Ana Rodriguez, Bill Miller, Cory Hitt, and Sarah Greer.

This interdisciplinary symposium brought together an international field of scholars of law, literature, and history whose research intersects with emotions and the law.

Selected papers from Emotions in the Courtroom are available via the CHE SoundCloud page.

<http://www.historyofemotions.org.au/events/emotions-in-the-courtroom.aspx>

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ROMA TRE AND TOR VERGATA UNIVERSITIES

Definizione del Corpo Comunitario: Pagare per Appartenere, Università degli Studi Roma Tre. Facoltà de Giurisprudenza, June 19, 2015.

<http://pimic.eu/pimic-rome-seminars/>

A Reading that shaped my research, Seminar PIMIC, Thursday May 21st and Thursday May 28th 2015 (with University of Roma Tre)

New methods and approaches: history and archeology of Byzantine Sicily, Seminar PIMIC, May 5th 2015, Speakers Alessandra Molinari (Università di Roma 'Tor Vergata'), Vivien Prigent (CNRS, Paris)

Gender impact: nuovi percorsi della storiografia, Seminar, 13th May 2013, PhD Program Storia e scienze filosofico-sociali, University of Rome Tor Vergata (prof. Cristina La Rocca, *Età medievale*)

La risoluzione dei conflitti: diritto, istituzioni, prassi, 30th-31st January 2014, PhD Program Storia e scienze filosofico-sociali, University of Rome Tor Vergata (prof. Massimo Vallerani, *Dispute, violenza, emozioni: paradigmi e trasformazioni della storiografia sui conflitti nella medievistica europea*).

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BIRKBECK COLLEGE

Birkbeck College's Seminar Series & Workshop : **Communicating Research in a Digital Environment**

GOLDEN IDOL FILMS

COMMUNICATING RESEARCH IN AN DIGITAL ENVIRONMENT

2nd – 4th July 2014

SEMINAR SERIES AND WORKSHOP

BACKGROUND

Golden Idol Films has been engaged to undertake three days of seminar teaching and practical workshops for seven students, all part of an EU funded multi-institution collaborative project called 'Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom' – PIMIC.

The aim of the project is to address a single question:

'Why did certain types of institutions come to characterise government and society in Christendom by the late Middle Ages, but not in the Islamic world, when the reverse might have been expected based on earlier periods?'

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

Birkbeck College's Summer Term PIMIC Secondments Series : **Rethinking Medieval Institutions.**

Rethinking Medieval Institutions

A seminar series on medieval institutions in a trans-regional perspective, funded by the EC research project "Power and Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom": an 'Initial Training Network' which combines academic research on medieval power and institutions with training in the wider dissemination of research-based knowledge, through a formal network established between universities and private sector companies
<http://www.pimic-itn.eu/>

08/05 - What is a Medieval Institution? Examples from Southern France

John Arnold (Birkbeck)

15/05 – Beyond the Sharia: The Development of Legal Institutions under the Mamluks, 1350 – 1517

Yossef Rapoport (QMUL)

22/05 – Conquerors, Brides and Concubines in Medieval Iberia: Interfaith Sex and Social Power

Simon Barton (Uni. Exeter)

05/06 – Institutions and Archives in the Arabic Eastern Mediterranean

Konrad Hirschler (SOAS) in discussion with Filippo de Vivo (Birkbeck)

12/06 – Institutions, History and Social Theory

David D'Avray (UCL)

26/06 – Researching Medieval Liturgy: Memory and Institutionalisation in an Exeter Manuscript

Sarah Hamilton (Uni. Exeter)

Time: 6:00 – 7:30 PM - Each talk will be followed by a discussion and wine reception
Location: Birkbeck College, Dreyfus Room (2.02), 28 Russell Square (enter via 26)

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

PIMIC FORUM

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVEAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

PIMIC Final Forum: 24-25 June, 2016, London

The PIMIC Final Forum (Power & Institutions in Medieval Islam and Christendom) was a two-day event for policy makers, journalists, lawyers, and academics. PIMIC has been a four-year project by leading scholars of Western, Byzantine and Islamic history examining the development of institutions in those regions. The Final Forum brought together international experts to discuss the modern institutional differences between the Islamic and Christian world through this never-before-considered lens: that of medieval history. The PIMIC project was the first of its kind, and the Final Forum aimed at generating dialogue and insights that will be crucial to policy-makers moving forward.

Highlights of the event include:

Opening Address:

- Prof. Dr. Malik Dahlan (Principal, Institution Quraysh for Law and Policy; Chief Lawyer, MRB Legal; International Chair of the Harvard Law School Association)

Policy Forum: The ‘Medieval’ Today—Reframing Institutional Complexity in the Modern World

Monica Hakimi (Professor of Law, University of Michigan Law School)

David Hendy (Professor of Media and Communication, University of Sussex)

Lena Salaymeh (Professor of Law, Tel Aviv University)

Charles Tripp (Professor of Politics with reference to the Middle East, SOAS)

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Keynote Lectures:

- “The Challenges of Institutional Development: Past and Present Issues” (Eduardo Manzano, CCHS-CSIC, Madrid)
- “Institutions and the Distribution of Expert Knowledge in Latin Europe, ca. 1100-1400” (Frank Rexroth, Professor of History, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen)
- “Document and Institutions in the Medieval Middle East: The Case of the Fatimids” (Marina Rustow, Khedouri A. Zilkha Professor of Jewish Civilisation in the Near East; Professor of Near Eastern Studies and History, Princeton)
- “Taking Control? Agency, Structure, and Social Praxis in Early Medieval Administration” (John Haldon, Professor of European History, Byzantine History, and Hellenic Studies, Princeton University)

[http://pimic.eu/pimic-itn-forum-enquiry-into-the-consequences-of-pimic-in-the-contemporary-world/#prettyphoto\[group\]/0/](http://pimic.eu/pimic-itn-forum-enquiry-into-the-consequences-of-pimic-in-the-contemporary-world/#prettyphoto[group]/0/)

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

PIMIC EXHIBITION

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

THE WAY WE ARE RULED. EXHIBITING INVISIBLE INSTITUTIONS

Introductory panel

Institutions are social artefacts. They are there because we make them. But in turn they make us, too. And they differ in time and space. They thus produce marked differences in historical trajectories.

Since they are part of people's own make up, it is hard to think beyond them. It is difficult to conceive of other forms of social organizations, other institutional landscapes. This is why we must think deeply about institutions. They are not just background noise or pre-existing frameworks, they are manifestations of power. They order and shape human lives, past and present.

In order to understand how such institutional landscapes are shaped, we must understand their history; and understanding their history means comprehending how institutions shaped differences and enabled interactions between societies.

The aim of the Exhibition *The Way We Are Ruled. Exhibiting Invisible Institutions* is to provide lasting outreach to PIMIC project's

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement no 316732

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training through the development of a travelling exhibition. This exhibition was first displayed within the context of the *PIMIC-ITN Forum. Inquiry into the Consequences of PIMIC in the Contemporary World*, held in London 24th and 25th, June 2016 and, in the same month, in the library of the University of St. Andrews. It consists of nine panels composed by maps, illustrations, textual and photographic material. All the texts have been written by the experts in the different areas of PIMIC. A real collaborative work among the members of the project.

A translated and expanded version of the exhibition played an important role in Madrid's Science Week 2016, and it will do it again in 2017, when it will be displayed at the Autónoma University of Madrid. The Spanish version will be also exhibited in a representative High School centre (Isabel la Católica, Madrid, March 2017) and in several cultural centres of the Madrid Region.

<http://pimic.eu/madrids-science-week-2016-pimic-exhibition/>

The Way We Are Ruled is also currently being translated to Italian. We expect it to travel around several universities and learning institutions in Italy.

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PIMIC at the Madrid's Science Week 2016

The Exhibition *The Way We Are Ruled. Exhibiting Invisible Institutions* is under licence Creative Commons and it can be freely dowloaded for any educational purpose.

<http://pimic.eu/the-way-we-are-ruled-exhibiting-invisible-institutions/>

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

THE INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF KNOWLEDGE

THE TRANSMISSION OF KNOWLEDGE, TEACHERS AND TRAVELLERS

The mobility of scholars in Islam

"Seek knowledge, far from home" — Muhammad (tradition)

The mobility of scholars in Islam was a key factor in the transmission of knowledge across the Islamic world. Scholars often traveled to study at the most renowned institutions, such as the House of Wisdom in Baghdad or the University of Cordoba in Spain. This movement of scholars facilitated the exchange of ideas and the spread of knowledge throughout the empire.

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Itinerant scholars in the West

In the West, itinerant scholars played a crucial role in the transmission of knowledge. These scholars traveled from one region to another, bringing with them the latest ideas and discoveries from the Islamic world. They often acted as teachers and mentors, spreading knowledge among the local population.

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THE WAY WE (ARE) RULED).
EXHIBITING INVISIBLE INSTITUTIONS.

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MIEVEAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

PIMIC COURSEWARE

POWER AND INSTITUTIONS IN MEDIEVAL ISLAM AND CHRISTENDOM

WHY INSTITUTIONS MATTER

COURSEWARE ON INSTITUTIONS IN THE MIDDLE AGES

<http://pimic.eu/why-institutions-matter-courseware-on-institutions-in-the-middle-ages/>

PIMIC courseware is a product result of the collaborative learning implemented in this project. It consists in a series of videos (interviews) thought as educational material developed by the PIMIC fellows, (from screenplay to filming) in collaboration with the members of the board. This is a work in progress since some videos are still on the editing process. They will be uploaded in our website in the near future.

[Gadi Algazi, University of Tel Aviv: What is an “institution” for the historian of the Mediterranean?](#)

[Michel Kaplan, Université Paris 1 - Panthéon- Sorbonne: How does the institutionalization of the monastic power take place in Byzantium?](#)

[John Hudson, University of St. Andrews: How would you define an institution for an historian of the 12th Century law?](#)

[Emanuele Conte, Università Roma Tre: How would you define an institution for an historian of the 12th Century law?](#)

[Emanuele Conte and John Hudson: A new relationship between legal codes and justice in the 12th century.](#)

[Alessandro Carocci, Università Roma Tor Vergata: What role did institutions play for social mobility?](#)

[Therese Martin, IH-CCHS-CSIC: How institutions are preserved and expressed via the medium of public building?](#)

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[Steve White, Emory College of Arts and Sciences: What are the norms of conflict resolution in the Middle Ages?](#)

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WEBSITE

www.pimic.eu

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In PIMIC we think that, also in science, communication should take place through a simple, intuitive and visually appealing website website.

We had put a big effort in designing a corporate image far from the romantic aesthetics of the Middle Ages and suitable for the three areas of study.

PIMIC website includes the crucial information about the project: who we are, what we do, how we do it and what are our results. It uses some subtle interactivity to get the visitors engaged in using the website, as it is the case of the presentation of the members of the project (WHO):

The website is also a showcase for the work of the members of the project, especially the fellows, whether it be a conference,

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[PIMIC at International Medieval Congress, Leeds, 2015](#)

[PIMIC at Leeds International Medieval Congress 2014](#)

a video or podcast, a project ID,

i. e. Sara Greer: <http://pimic.eu/who/#!/sarah-greer>

or a blog post:

[Manstetten ESR10. SOAS University of London. UK, Knowledge and Authority in Medieval Syria \(mid-tenth - mid-twelfth century\). The transmission of learning in a period of institutionalisation.](#)

[Viale. ESR9. University of Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne. France, The Papacy and the Political and Ecclesiastical Institutions of the Byzantine Empire. \(6th-8th Centuries\)](#)

[Attilio Stella. ESR8. University of Tel Aviv. Israel](#)

[Attilio Stella. Lordship and City Commune: Forging Bonds with the Country](#)

[Tommi Lankila. ESR7. Università degli Studi Roma Tor Vergata. Rome, Italy. "God sent the avenging pagans"](#)

[Bech Olsen. ESR6. Birkbeck College London. UK.](#)

[Jasmin Hauck ESR5. Università degli Studi Roma Tre. Rome, Italy. Florentine marriage dispensations, 1460-1530: A socio-legal history](#)

[Cory Hitt ESR4. University of St. Andrews. UK](#)

[Sarah Greer. ESR3. University of St. Andrews. UK](#)

[Sara Greer. Making a historical documentary or: how I learned to stop worrying about footnotes](#)

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[Evgeniya Shelina. ESR1. CCHS-CSIC Madrid, Spain](#)

[Evgeniya Shelina. Mawlid, Christmas, Noël, Natividad, Weihnachts, Рождество ... The Celebration of Birth](#)

[John Hudson. The Octocentenary Year of Magna Carta](#)

